

Chemical Examination of *Cassia fistula*

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The present work was taken up following the antiviral activity found during the screening programme at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

The air dried, powdered stem bark (2 kg) was percolated exhaustively with alcohol (8 litres). The concentrated alcoholic extract was then partitioned between 70% alcohol and benzene. The benzene layer was separated and concentrated. The alcoholic residue was then extracted with n-butanol. The n-butanol extract displayed antiviral activity and was found to contain tannins. The benzene extract (5 gm. green viscous mass) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with chloroform and alcohol gave crystalline fractions, I, II & III. Fraction I crystallised from acetone, m.p. $205^{\circ} (\alpha)_D + 20^{\circ}$ (CHCl_3). (Found C, 84.21; H, 11.45. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C; 84.57; H, 11.73) responded to Noller test and displayed unsaturation (tetranitromethane test). Its identity with lupeol was established by preparing its benzoate, m.p. $265^{\circ} (\alpha)_D + 62^{\circ}$ (CHCl_3) and determining the mixed m.p. with authentic lupeol benzoate. Fraction II crystallised from acetone-methanol, m.p. $136^{\circ} (\alpha)_D - 34^{\circ}$ (CHCl_3), gave Liebermann-Burchard test. It was identified as β -sitosterol by preparing its acetate, m.p. $132^{\circ} (\alpha)_D - 40^{\circ}$ (CHCl_3). (Found C, 81.40; H, 11.52, $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.57; H, 11.40) and mixed m.p. with authentic β -sitosterol acetate. Fraction III was crystallised from acetone, m.p. $79-80^{\circ}$. The identity of this compound as hexacosanol has been proved by preparing its acetate, m.p. 65° . (Found C 79.12; H, 12.0. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_2$ requires. C, 79.24; H, 13.20) and mixed, m.p. with an authentic sample of hexacosanyl acetate.

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